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FINANCIAL MECHANISMS FOR STIMULATING INVESTMENTS IN THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE RUSSIAN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY: THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

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The article presents the results of a theoretical and methodological study of financial mechanisms for stimulating investment in the sustainable development of the Russian construction industry. The relevance of the study stems from systemic problems in the financial support of the construction industry, exacerbated by macroeconomic instability, high risk saturation, and the need to integrate sustainable development principles (ESG). The article identifies the evolutionary trajectory of financial mechanisms in construction—from traditional lending to comprehensive models integrating stakeholder value and ESG principles. It also systematizes the impact of key institutional changes (the transition to escrow accounts, the development of green financing) on the investment attractiveness of the industry. The role of financial innovations (green bonds, sustainable tied loans, project financing) as drivers of the transition to green and energy-efficient construction is substantiated. The discussion critically evaluates the applicability of foreign theoretical models to Russian institutional realities. Scientific conclusions are formulated, defining the theoretical foundation for subsequent empirical and analytical work within the framework of the study. Prospects for further research are identified, including empirical verification of the proposed theoretical positions and the development of applied models for assessing effectiveness.

Keywords: investment decisions, financial risks, financial innovations, project finance, construction industry, financial instruments, sustainable development, ESG, green bonds, institutional environment.

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